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REGULATORNI IZAZOVI DIGITALNIH VALUTA CENTRALNIH BANAKA – SLUČAJ EURA

Razvoj interneta je nesumnjivo podigao životni standard i učinio ekonomiju, obradu podataka i komunikaciju efikasnijom, dok su mnoga pitanja u vezi sa ljudskim pravima – posebno pravom na privatnost i lične slobode, zaštitom od nezakonitog nadzora, novim oblicima kriminalnih aktivnosti i udruživanja itd. postala relevantna. Jedan od sektora koji će verovatno imati najviše koristi od digitalne transformacije jeste međunarodna trgovina i samo poslovanje. Digitalna valuta centralne banke (CBDC) je oblik digitalne valute koju proizvodi i garantuje centralna banka kao zakonsko sredstvo plaćanja – novac. Štaviše, CBDC se može razlikovati od kriptovaluta i po korišćenju tehnološkoj platformi. Digitalna valuta CBDC možda fundamentalno ne koristi distribuiranu decentralizovanu bazu podataka (obično blokčejn u slučaju kriptovaluta), koju karakteriše decentralizovana priroda i nedostatak centralnog autoriteta. Za CBDC možemo očekivati centralni autoritet u obliku centralne banke. Koncept CBDC-a je prvenstveno da se što većem broju ekonomskih agenata na tržištu pruži stabilna, sajber bezbedna, brza, jeftina i lako dostupna verzija plaćanja, prvenstveno na maloprodajnom tržištu. CBDC-ovi bi mogli dovesti do jeftinijih prekograničnih transakcija, za razliku od elektronskih transakcija pod pokroviteljstvom komercijalnih banaka. CBDC takođe odgovara na trend opa-

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danja upotrebe gotovine. Glavni cilj ovog rada je da se istraži i ispita ova nova tehnologija, relevantna regulativa za uvođenje CBDC-a u evrozoni i njen uticaj na ekonomsku aktivnost, monetarnu politiku i ljudska prava analizirajući finansijski instrument u nastajanju – digitalni evro.

Ključne reči: Digitalna valuta centralne banke (CBDC), digitalni evro, Evropska centralna banka (ECB).

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Regulatory Challenges of Central Bank Digital Currencies: The Case of Euro

The development of the Internet has unquestionably raised the standard of living and made the economy, data processing and communication more efficient, while many questions regarding human rights, especially the right of privacy and personal freedoms, protection from unlawful surveillance, new forms of criminal activities and associations (etc.), became relevant. One of the sectors that is likely to benefit most from digital transformation is the international trade and business itself. A Central bank digital currency (CBDC) is a form of digital currency that is manufactured and guaranteed by a central bank as a legal tender – money. Furthermore, a CBDC may also differ from cryptocurrencies in the technology platform used. A CBDC may not fundamentally use a distributed decentralised database (typically blockchain in the case of cryptocurrencies), which is characterised by its decentralised nature and a lack of central authority. For a CBDC, we can expect a central authority in the form of a central bank. The CBDC concept is primarily to bring a stable, cybersecure, fast, cheap and easily accessible version of payment primarily in the retail market to as many economic agents in the market as possible. CBDCs could lead to cheaper cross-border transactions, as opposed to electronic transactions under the auspices of commercial banks. A CBDC also responds to the receding trend towards the use of cash. The main aim of this paper is to investigate and examine this new technology, relevant regulation for the introduction of CBDC in the Eurozone and its impacts

on economic activity, monetary policy and human rights by analysing a nascent financial instrument – digital euro.

Keywords: Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), digital euro, European Central Bank (ECB).